

Low-Dimensional Functional Materials for Catalysis and Energy Storage

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Functional low-dimensional materials with judicious hetero- and single-atom engineering may unlock versatile platforms for high-performance electrochemical energy storage and efficient, earth-abundant catalysis. In the first part of the talk, I will trace how tailored graphene derivatives and organic architectures push the limits of batteries and supercapacitors. Examples include nitrogen-superdoped graphene with diamond-like interlayer bonds that reaches benchmark volumetric energies;¹ graphene acid whose dense carboxylation raises its lithium-ion capacity beyond high-quality single layer graphene;² and self-assembled organic nanowire Li-ion anodes that store up to 1900 mAh g⁻¹.³ Such graphene derivatives also enable direct up-cycling of spent sorbents for water purification into electrodes for energy storage, mitigating costs and wastes through circular design and sustainable resource management principles.⁴

The second part highlights catalytic technologies that exploit materials of similar design, which are key to decreasing the energy and environmental footprint of the chemicals industry. An aminoacid-anchored graphene acid organocatalyst outperforms homogeneous acids for solvent-free valorization of waste organics and for biofuel production.⁵ Embedding earth abundant transition metal atoms in such graphene derivatives affords redox-switchable mixed-valence catalysts that efficiently drive aerobic oxidative transformations of lower-value molecules to key chemicals for the pharmaceutical and polymer industry.⁶ Together, these studies demonstrate how molecularly functionalized materials and metal-carbon seamless architectures can deliver advances in catalysis for low energy organic transformations and electrochemical energy storage technologies.

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